

PEDAGOGICAL CONDITIONS OF FORMATION OF COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE OF ELEMENTARY SCHOOL STUDENTS BASED ON FOLK GAMES

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Orcid ID: 0009-0001-3085-7668

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11197647>

Abstract: In this article, the pedagogical conditions of forming the communicative competence of elementary school students based on folk games are studied, and the stages of its formation are analyzed.

Key words: pedagogue, professional competence, classification, improvement, competence, competent approach, communicative, folk games.

INTRODUCTION. Today, the tasks of reforming primary education, introducing new approaches to it, and implementing concepts affecting the quality and effectiveness of education are becoming urgent. As one of the important approaches in this regard, there is an increasing need to integrate folk games into primary education, to use folk games in organizing the education of students.

To what extent are we using the positive educational opportunities of folk games to form social and cultural skills in students? What are the main developmental goals of folk movement games? First of all, each game is structured in a simple, psychologically interesting way, and high human feelings such as nationalism, kindness, bravery, patriotism, tolerance, self-sacrifice are embedded in its essence.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS. Specialists have been paying special attention to the problem of using folk games and didactic lessons to improve the effectiveness of education. Among the scientists of our republic are M.Abdullajonova, B.R.Adizov, A.Y.Bobomurodova, O.Jamoldinova, B.Ziyomuhamedov, G.Ibragimova, R.Ishmuhamedov, U.I.Mahkamov, M.H.Mahmudov, O.Musurmonova, D.Sharipova, Sh.Sharipov, N.M.Egamberdiyeva. this was reflected in his works.

From foreign scientists A. Yolanda, N. Nicotera, A. Christopher, L. Botcheva, J. Shih, L. C. Huffman, L. D. Breeman, van Lier, Theo Wubbels, R. Sears, J. L. Spilt, E. Vervoort, A. Koenen, F. Clemente, A. Amutio, L. Gonzalez's studies have explored the possibilities of games in the formation of social skills and basic competencies.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION. At various stages of development, representatives of the older generation constantly taught the young people their accumulated knowledge and experience, their attitude to their hobby, and gradually created a connection. As a result, the motivation, need, desire for physical education among young people has increased, and this situation has become normal. If we carefully study the folk movement games and see and get to know each of them, we will see how much spiritual and psychological power they have in raising the representatives of the young generation to be physically and mentally strong and healthy in all respects. So, in the process of physical education of students, there are wide possibilities of folk movement games, and if they are used effectively, the positive psychological impact of the games will increase. Thus, the action games created by the nation

combine with work, national psychology, lifestyle, nature of the environment, ecology, cultural heritage, traditions, customs, ethnopsychological features, and universal values of the people and create a wonderful balance.

Students can be encouraged to learn and cooperate only when the learning process is organized correctly. Games are of particular importance in surprising students, making them interested in mastering educational materials and encouraging them to be creative in a conscious way.

In order for games and educational activities based on games to provide an opportunity to achieve the expected effectiveness, it is necessary to correctly define what tasks can be solved in the process of their implementation. The organization of such games should be started from the elementary grades as much as possible. Educators and psychologists say that if the student is not interested, the acquired knowledge will not have a positive effect on his emotions and will not serve his intellectual development. Also, students cannot establish beneficial cooperation with their classmates in the process of mastering this knowledge.

The game is a means of knowledge, creativity, and spiritual-intellectual development of students. With the help of the game, a new world opens up to students. It is impossible to fully develop students without using the game. In the process of the game, students master the system of mutual relations, enter into cooperation, develop and form as individuals. The game has special value as a complex social-cultural and didactic phenomenon, and has been the object of many philosophical-cultural, pedagogical-psychological studies. Games play a special role in establishing communication between students. Its complexity is determined by the uniqueness of game activity in the pedagogical process. Their special pedagogical value, freedom and voluntariness are recognized as the unique features of games. Games are practically oriented and have special pedagogical value as they serve to obtain a guaranteed result.

Games are distinguished by their multitasking, as well as by having different content and appearance. There are different approaches to classifying games. Most of them are based on the existing parts of the games. Many experts have tried to describe games in three large groups: games based on ready-made and strict rules; free games, the rules of which are formed during the game process itself, and games based on rules that are partly fixed and partly formed during the game.

However, the above indicators are conditional in nature, and there is an opportunity to approach each game creatively. In this process, participants are required to follow certain rules. The following groups can be distinguished as independent forms of play: all kinds of children's games; holiday games; folk games; theatrical game actions; game training and exercises; questionnaires and tests in the form of a game; games based on humor; competitions, debates, confrontations, competitive games, contests, relays; wedding traditions, game-based customs; cheat games, winning games, prize games; carnivals, game-like auctions, etc.

O'yinlar jarayonida o'quvchilar o'zlariga do'stlar, sheriklar, yaqin hamfikrlar tanlash imkoniyatiga ega bo'ladi. O'yinning ijtimoiy-pedagogik ahamiyati aynan shunda namoyon bo'ladi. O'qituvchi o'z maqsadiga erishish uchun o'quv jarayoni va o'yin faoliyati orasida qarama-qarshilik bo'lmasligi lozim.

According to its content and forms, the educational process should not be boring or boring for the student. As a didactic process, the content of the game includes: roles assumed by the participants of the game; game actions that serve to fulfill these roles; items that help to perform actions during the game; specific actions between the subjects of the game process; the content of the game, i.e. the plot, the truthful, real life conditionally expressed in it. In the course of the games, students gradually learn moral standards, develop the skills of responsibility for performing actions.

Games have two important features: a) development of oral speech of game participants; b) accustoming students to perceive the essence of certain situations. A number of games can be used in the course of the lesson to form and regularly develop such skills in students.

It is known that games are described by types. In particular, according to the purpose, according to the number of participants, according to the nature of expressing reality. In pedagogy, there are imitative, symbolic, research-based games. The main character of games is determined by the modeling of students' mental labor activities in connection with game activities and the formation of a process based on clear symbols and rules, as well as new knowledge and methods of activity.

In this direction, the following are identified: 1) interactive games that have a direct impact on the textbook; these include rebuses, crosswords, scanwords, chainsaws; 2) games that affect students; these include action, role-playing and simulation games; 3) non-interactive games; individual tasks of a game character are among them.

Experts tried to classify games according to their level during execution: 1) role-playing and story games; 2) games based on clear rules and having a useful plot; 3) games without a plot. For example, crosswords, scanwords, chainwords.

In general, experts divide games into plot, role-playing, action, imitation and dramatized games. It is clear from the above-mentioned classifications that each classification has a certain idea. Educators have clearly distinguished the differences between games and external rules that determine their content. At the same time, there are also games based on the internal logic of the modeled process. These games differ from each other not only in their purpose and content, but also have their own importance in influencing the intellectual and emotional spheres of students. Design games differ from each other in their didactic capabilities. They are divided into the following types:

1) games in the form of reconstruction help to demonstrate reality, perceive existing situations, and express the demands of a certain society;

2) games of a formal-project nature, in the process of these games, students make a personal assessment of social reality, in which they rely on cognitive experiences;

3) informal design games, these games create a wide-scale basis for the expansion of students' imaginations and activities, in which they act based on concrete reality. At the same time, there is a need for a wider didactic description of retrospective games.

Differentiating games should be based on the following three criteria:

a) specific aspects of the roles performed by students;

b) conditions of occurrence of perceived situations in training;

c) improvisation of students during the game and the existing scenario of the game.

One of the important types of games are games based on the algorithm of students' activities. Most pedagogues call them training games. Among such games:

- 1) table games, including chess, dominoes, lotto, field of miracles;
- 2) games based on algorithms, such as rebuses, crosswords, puzzles, chainwords;
- 3) games with a plot focused on the perception of reality based on training.

These games were analyzed to a certain extent by didactic experts, and in the course of our research, we focused on opening up their pedagogical possibilities in forming students' cooperative skills based on friendly relations.

The implementation of games in the educational process is directly related to game technologies. It is known that the theoretical and empirical foundations of game technologies are not sufficiently developed. Therefore, solving the following tasks in this process is of particular importance:

development of invariant technologies of game organization, implementation in educational practice, paying special attention to its parameters in the process of game organization;

organization of games in different forms and determining the level of efficiency;

development of games that help students to work in harmony, engage in communication, study, and show the qualities of work and determine their effectiveness by testing them in an experiment;

organizing games, putting them into practice, determining the specific aspects of the teacher's activity in determining their effectiveness.

An attempt was made to rely on a number of parameters in the organization of the games. These are the names of the games, the intended purpose of their use, the materials and tools used in the process of the games, the items necessary for the organization of the games, the rules of the game, etc. All this allowed the students to have a general idea about the game process. At the same time, special attention was paid to pedagogically important didactic opportunities. In this case, as an instruction: a) during a certain communication process; b) in cases aimed at the implementation of cooperation; c) we paid attention to students' implementation of forms of social cooperation.

The above-mentioned parameters were of particular importance in the organization of the games. Such games were mainly organized for the purpose of preparing students for careers and social life. We tried to implement cooperation, first of all, on the basis of communication among students. During the games, we paid attention to students' acquisition of communication skills. For this, we turned to the technology of organizing and conducting a number of games based on active communication.

We paid attention to the fact that this technology meets a number of requirements. These requirements are: 1) taking into account the possibilities of communication during the game; 2) pay attention to the fact that games are a phenomenon that harmonizes the worldview of students; 3) organizing the activities of the teacher in the preparation of games.

We paid attention to the expression of the following parameters in the content of the games: having didactic possibilities of the game; acquisition of students' communicative skills; that the games are aimed at inculcating in students the specific features of communicativeness and friendly communication; communicative orientation of games; representation of games as a form of social communication; such as the rules of conducting games and their didactic equipment.

In order to create forms of communication, special attention was paid to the following: 1) intended communication of students; 2) intended forms of cooperation.

The intended communication of students was carried out in the form of requests and information. The pedagogical significance of forms of communication is that they represent the orientation of students towards a specific goal. For example: a) emergence of the spoken opinion; b) managing the activities of partners in the communication process; c) create a basis for dialogue; g) to create skills and competences in using speech tools in certain situations of communication; d) ensuring the emergence of stable tendencies; e) such as being able to find independent solutions to problematic situations.

CONCLUSION. One of the important issues is to clearly define what skills students should acquire during the games: effective competition and cooperation; conduct negotiations; successful implementation and completion of work; conflict management; control and regulate one's emotions in stressful situations; they master skills such as establishing an effective cooperative environment within the team.

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